

at 7 and 3 days before inoculation (by the method of Purkayastha and Ray Chaudhuri) to 9-week-old semidwarfs Jaya and TN1 significantly reduced sheath rot disease. The treatment also increased plant height. For Jaya, the control was 54.6 cm high; the plant with 100 ppm GA was 83.8 cm. For TN1, the control was 57.2 cm; the plant with 100 ppm GA was 76.7 cm. The length of internodes also increased (Jaya: 7.1 cm for the control, 12.9 cm with 100 ppm GA; TN1: 6.4 cm for the control, 10.81 cm with 100 ppm GA). Low concentrations of GA stimulated mycelial growth (increase of 11.44% with 0.1 µg/ml and 4.8% with 1 µg/ml); higher concentrations (10 and 100 µg/ml) inhibited growth (4.5% and 9.3% reduction, respectively) of the pathogen *in vitro*. Although 100 ppm GA inhibited

pathogen growth and decreased disease intensity considerably, it is not clear whether that was a direct effect of GA on the pathogen within the host tissue or was due to changes induced by GA in the plants' growth pattern. Amin and associates pointed out in 1974 that dwarf cultivars were prone to sheath rot probably because of their short internodes. Treatment of noninoculated (healthy) leaf sheaths with GA (100 µg/ml) initially enhanced the amino acid level (Jaya, 7.6%; TN1, 9.3% increase in relation to untreated, non-inoculated control) but decreased it considerably 7 days after inoculation of untreated plants (Jaya, 29.4%; TN1, 32.3% decrease in relation to untreated, non-inoculated control, on the basis of detected amino acids and amides). In the case of GA-treated plants, the amino

acid level also decreased 7 days after inoculation (Jaya, 19.3%; TN1, 23.1%).

The amino acids and amides were estimated by the method described by Purkayastha and Mukhopadhyay in 1976. In addition, total phenol contents of leaf sheaths were measured by the method of Folin-Denis. Colorimetric studies revealed that total phenol levels were markedly higher in untreated infected leaf sheaths (by 145.9% in Jaya and by 126.7% in TN1) than in the control and slightly after GA (100 µg/ml) treatment. But ferulic acid significantly increased in treated leaf sheaths. The application of GA may cause biochemical changes in host plants, but it undoubtedly creates a condition unfavorable for the growth of invading parasites. ■

Effect of chemicals on parasitic nematode populations and yields in continuously cropped uplands

S. A. Raymundo, plant pathologist; M. D. Thomas, research officer; and A. S. Fofie, field technician, Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone, West Africa

After monitoring nematode populations at Makassa, the upland experimental site of the Rokupr Rice Research Station, a progressive buildup of parasitic nematode populations was noted. In the 1979 cropping season, the 6th successive year that the site was planted to rice, the number of plant parasitic nematodes averaged 1,034/100 cc of rhizospheric soil among plots planted to cultivar TOX502-13-SLR. The recovered nematodes and their relative proportions were *Pratylenchus* sp., 2%; *Helicotylenchus* sp., 25%; *Criconemoides* sp., 21%; *Tylenchus* sp., 16%; *Rotylenchulus* sp., 5%; and *Aphelenchus* sp., 4%. The corresponding figure per 10-g root sample was 219, distributed as follows: *Pratylenchus*, 34%; *Helicotylenchus* sp., 32%; and *Criconemoides*, 34%.

A study to determine the effects of DD, Mocap, and carbofuran on nematode populations and yields was conducted in the 1979 season. DD was applied by pouring a measured quantity into

Table 1. Number of plant parasite nematodes in rhizospheric soil and roots at harvest, Sierra Leone.

Treatment	Application	Plant parasitic nematodes (no./100 cc rhizospheric soil)		Plant parasitic nematodes (no./10-g root)	
		TOX502-13-SLR	LAC23	TOX502-13-SLR	LAC23
Control	—	1034	710	219	188
DD	303 liters/ha	689	460	123	102
Mocap	56 kg/ha	597	542	132	106
Carbofuran	31 kg/ha	653	494	120	101
LSD (0.05)		176	49.6	27.4	28.5
CV (%)		14.9	3.2	11.6	11.4

previously prepared holes, 20–30cm deep and 15 cm apart, 2 weeks before seeding. A 1:2 Mocap-sand mixture was prepared and broadcast evenly before sowing. Carbofuran granules, also applied before sowing, were broadcast evenly without mixing with sand.

The cultivars LAC23 and TOX502-13-SLR were used separately. Plots were laid in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The plants were raised following recommended cultural and management practices.

At harvest, the nematode populations in rhizospheric soil and on roots were determined.

All three chemicals significantly reduced parasitic nematode populations in rhizospheric soil and in the roots of both cultivars (Table 1). More nematodes were recovered from the rhizospheric soil than from the roots. All chemicals

Table 2. Grain yield of two cultivars, Sierra Leone.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	TOX502-13-SLR	LAC23
Control	1.4	1.9
DD	2.5	3.6
Mocap	2.1	2.4
Furadan	2.2	2.8
LSD (0.05)	0.5	1.1
CV (%)	16.5	26.5

significantly increased the yields of TOX502-13-SLR, but only DD significantly increased the yields of LAC23 (Table 2). ■

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.